

Supplementary materials

A. Time course of smoothness and upper extremity motor impairment scores, an overview of all time points against each other.

Time course of SPARC post stroke

SPARC	Week 1			Week 2			Week 3			Week 4		
	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P
Week 1	-	-	-									
Week 2	0.08	[0.01 – 0.14]	0.017	-	-	-						
Week 3	0.17	[0.11 – 0.23]	<0.001	0.09	[0.03 – 0.14]	0.002	-	-	-			
Week 4	0.20	[0.13 – 0.26]	<0.001	0.12	[0.06 – 0.18]	<0.001	0.03	[-0.02 – 0.08]	0.245	-	-	-
Week 5	0.21	[0.15 – 0.27]	<0.001	0.13	[0.08 – 0.19]	<0.001	0.04	[-0.01 – 0.09]	0.083	0.01	[-0.04 – 0.07]	0.624
Week 8	0.23	[0.17 – 0.29]	<0.001	0.15	[0.09 – 0.21]	<0.001	0.06	[0.01 – 0.12]	0.019	0.03	[-0.02 – 0.09]	0.254
Week 12	0.24	[0.18 – 0.31]	<0.001	0.16	[0.11 – 0.22]	<0.001	0.08	[0.03 – 0.13]	0.003	0.04	[-0.01 – 0.10]	0.094
Week 26	0.26	[0.20 – 0.32]	<0.001	0.18	[0.13 – 0.23]	<0.001	0.09	[0.04 – 0.14]	<0.001	0.06	[0.01 – 0.11]	0.025
	Week 5			Week 8			Week 12			Week 26		
	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P
Week 1												
Week 2												
Week 3												
Week 4												
Week 5	-	-	-									
Week 8	0.02	[-0.03 – 0.07]	0.478	-	-	-						
Week 12	0.03	[-0.02 – 0.08]	0.210	0.01	[-0.04 – 0.07]	0.623	-	-	-			
Week 26	0.05	[-0.00 – 0.10]	0.062	0.03	[-0.02 – 0.08]	0.290	0.01	[-0.04 – 0.06]	0.558	-	-	-

Abbreviations: B, regression coefficient; 95%-CI, 95% confidence interval; P, probability value; SPARC, spectral arc length adapted.

Time course of FM-UE post stroke

FM-UE	Week 1			Week 2			Week 3			Week 4		
	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P
Week 1	-	-	-									
Week 2	11.59	[8.81 – 14.37]	<0.001	-	-	-						
Week 3	16.01	[13.02 – 19.01]	<0.001	4.42	[1.38 – 7.46]	0.005	-	-	-			
Week 4	18.22	[15.29 – 21.16]	<0.001	6.63	[3.65 – 9.62]	<0.001	2.21	[-0.97 – 5.40]	0.173	-	-	-
Week 5	18.86	[16.12 – 21.59]	<0.001	7.27	[4.47 – 10.07]	<0.001	2.85	[-0.16 – 5.85]	0.063	0.64	[-2.31 – 3.58]	0.674
Week 8	20.53	[17.68 – 23.38]	<0.001	8.94	[6.03 – 11.85]	<0.001	4.52	[1.41 – 7.63]	0.005	2.31	[-0.75 – 5.36]	0.138
Week 12	20.82	[18.04 – 23.60]	<0.001	9.23	[6.39 – 12.07]	<0.001	4.81	[1.77 – 7.85]	0.002	2.60	[-0.38 – 5.58]	0.087
Week 26	21.48	[18.76 – 24.19]	<0.001	9.89	[7.11 – 12.67]	<0.001	5.46	[2.47 – 8.46]	<0.001	3.25	[0.32 – 6.18]	0.030
	Week 5			Week 8			Week 12			Week 26		
	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P	B	95%-CI	P
Week 1												
Week 2												
Week 3												
Week 4												
Week 5	-	-	-									
Week 8	1.67	[-1.19 – 4.53]	0.251	-	-	-						
Week 12	1.96	[-0.83 – 4.75]	0.168	0.29	[-2.61 – 3.19]	0.844	-	-	-			
Week 26	2.62	[-0.12 – 5.35]	0.061	0.94	[-1.91 – 3.79]	0.515	0.66	[-2.12 – 3.43]	0.643	-	-	-

Abbreviations: B, regression coefficient; 95%-CI, 95% confidence interval; P, probability value; FM-UE, Fugl-Meyer motor assessment of the upper extremity.

B. Overview of data used for statistical analyses: kinematics, clinical scores and patient characteristics.

Kinematics - smoothness

SPARC of stroke patients at each measurement moment

ID	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 8	Week 12	Week 26
1	-1.518		-1.414		-1.466			-1.415
2	-1.540	-1.477	-1.512		-1.471	-1.454	-1.482	-1.463
3			-1.482		-1.508	-1.460	-1.506	-1.500
4		-2.038	-1.789		-2.097	-1.784	-1.720	-1.642
5		-1.517	-1.454	-1.448	-1.479	-1.449	-1.427	-1.451
6		-1.543	-1.517	-1.525	-1.488	-1.448	-1.458	-1.566
7	-2.008	-1.562	-1.566	-1.481	-1.468	-1.450	-1.458	-1.439
8	-1.562	-1.427	-1.426	-1.410	-1.435		-1.441	-1.425
9	-1.716	-1.716	-1.654	-1.548	-1.677	-1.646	-1.567	-1.572
10	-1.516	-1.547	-1.451		-1.462	-1.532	-1.476	-1.443
11	-1.452		-1.462	-1.442	-1.421	-1.422	-1.415	-1.423
12	-2.413		-1.475	-1.479	-1.498	-1.446	-1.443	-1.429
13			-1.754	-1.750	-1.744	-1.565	-1.479	-1.441
14	-1.632	-1.499	-1.436	-1.479	-1.508	-1.479	-1.497	-1.463
15	-1.866	-1.481	-1.578	-1.453	-1.514	-1.421	-1.444	-1.443
16		-1.475	-1.423	-1.425	-1.409	-1.431	-1.420	-1.478
17			-1.863	-1.546	-1.444	-1.542	-1.446	-1.433
18	-1.649	-1.602	-1.557	-1.551	-1.592		-1.554	-1.547
19			-1.523	-1.461	-1.467	-1.519	-1.493	-1.441
20			-1.700	-2.160	-1.587	-1.445	-1.439	-1.429
21	-1.510	-1.487	-1.508	-1.484	-1.422	-1.497	-1.486	-1.436
22			-1.859	-1.526	-1.516	-1.611	-1.492	-1.497
23	-2.105	-1.809	-1.661	-1.483	-1.559		-1.447	-1.548
24		-1.939	-1.540	-1.545	-1.477	-1.487	-1.494	-1.522
25	-1.957	-1.612	-1.600	-1.631	-1.565	-1.577	-1.644	-1.541
26	-1.737	-1.520	-1.544	-1.516	-1.531	-1.525	-1.523	-1.441
27		-2.206	-1.522	-1.484	-1.457	-1.433	-1.435	-1.437
28	-1.778	-1.648	-1.601	-1.548	-1.529	-1.460	-1.545	-1.415
29		-1.657	-1.647	-1.550	-1.519	-1.539	-1.482	-1.543
30	-1.543	-1.482			-1.410			-1.417
31	-1.640	-1.579	-1.601	-1.540	-1.514	-1.533	-1.588	-1.485
32		-1.798	-1.581	-1.563	-1.566	-1.487	-1.525	-1.470
33	-1.641	-1.694	-1.631	-1.803	-1.661	-1.625	-1.673	-1.640
34		-1.930	-1.707	-1.456	-1.567	-1.503	-1.460	-1.497
35			-1.591	-1.584	-1.483	-1.531	-1.527	-1.486
36	-1.593	-1.544	-1.522	-1.449	-1.480	-1.512	-1.442	-1.414
37		-1.479	-1.593	-1.570	-1.575		-1.542	-1.500
38		-1.677		-1.569	-1.583	-1.599	-1.549	-1.525
39		-1.534	-1.491		-1.475	-1.502	-1.507	-1.477
40		-2.231	-1.496	-1.451	-1.432		-1.425	-1.452

SPARC of healthy age and gender matched individuals

ID	Mean	Std
H1	-1.430	0.012
H2	-1.412	0.005
H3	-1.462	0.062
H4	-1.446	0.045
H5	-1.414	0.008
H6	-1.420	0.010
H7	-1.424	0.015
H8	-1.409	0.006
H9	-1.434	0.011
H10	-1.461	0.078
H11	-1.480	0.055
H12	-1.437	0.047

Abbreviations: SPARC, spectral arc length adapted; ID, subject number; std, standard deviation.

Clinical scores

FM-UE of stroke patients at each measurement moment

ID	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 8	Week 12	Week 26
1	60	62		65	66			66
2	46	48		48	46	47	50	54
3	47	51		56	60	62	60	56
4	34	39	41		44	49	56	57
5	55			63	64	63	64	64
6	9	50	64	63	65	66	66	66
7	46	55	59	62	62	59	60	63
8	53	62	65	66	66		66	66
9	52	61	61	61	62		63	66
10	60	65	66	66	66	66	66	66
11	60	64		65	66	66	66	66
12	39	47	58	63	62	62	62	59
13	19	35	43	45	46	47	51	63
14	60	62	63	63	63	64	65	64
15	58	60	61	62	63	64	64	64
16	58	65	66		66	66	66	66
17	35		50	62	62	65	66	65
18	30	52	53	53	49		44	49
19	63	65	65	66	66	66	66	66
20	23	45	49	52	62	65	66	66
21	62	63	63	64	65	64	64	65
22	5	26		53	56	58	59	59
23	35	49	53	58	59	63	63	59
24	13	41	45	49	51	62	63	65
25	18	49	51	54	54	56	55	56
26	38	52	61	62	64		64	65
27	35				63	65	65	65
28	43	48	55	54	57	59	59	61
29	19	28		51	55	58	58	58
30	48	51						56
31	44	49	56	56	56	56	63	64
32	31	41	46		46	52	48	49
33	38	42	42		41	35	39	47
34	44	49	50		52	57	60	63
35	29	46	55		57	58		60
36	46	60	60	61	63	63	62	61
37	27	51	60	64	64	66	66	63
38	48	60		62	63	63	64	63
39	56	58			62	65	65	65
40	11	47	52	54	58	62	58	60

Abbreviations: FM-UE, Fugl-Meyer motor assessment of the upper extremity [0 – 66]; ID, patient number.

Patient characteristics

ID	Sex (male/female)	Age	Affected body side (left/right)	Hand dominance (left/right/forced right)	Bamford classification (LACI/PACI/TACI)
1	female	57	left	right	LACI
2	male	67	right	right	PACI
3	female	45	left	right	TACI
4	male	54	left	right	LACI
5	male	32	left	right	LACI
6	male	71	right	right	PACI
7	male	62	left	left	LACI
8	female	79	right	right	LACI
9	female	74	left	right	LACI
10	male	38	left	right	LACI
11	female	64	right	forced right	LACI
12	female	75	right	right	LACI
13	male	51	right	right	LACI
14	female	74	left	right	LACI
15	female	63	left	right	LACI
16	female	71	left	right	LACI
17	male	39	right	right	PACI
18	male	64	left	right	PACI
19	male	56	left	right	PACI
20	male	41	right	right	LACI
21	male	36	left	right	LACI
22	male	56	left	right	LACI
23	male	50	left	right	PACI
24	male	63	left	right	LACI
25	female	57	left	right	LACI
26	female	52	right	right	LACI
27	female	40	left	right	LACI
28	male	69	right	right	LACI
29	male	44	right	left	PACI
30	female	70	left	right	LACI
31	female	69	right	right	PACI
32	female	46	left	right	TACI
33	female	68	left	right	LACI
34	male	73	right	right	PACI
35	male	60	left	right	LACI
36	male	66	left	right	LACI
37	female	51	left	right	LACI
38	male	65	left	right	LACI
39	male	59	right	right	LACI
40	female	72	right	right	LACI

Abbreviations: ID, patient number; LACI, lacunar anterior circular infarct; PACI, partial anterior circular infarct; TACI, total anterior circular infarct.

C. Fugl-Meyer assessment of the upper extremity – without hand scores

Sub-analysis of time course of Fugl-Meyer while hand scores were ignored, and its longitudinal association with SPARC. This refers to a sub-analysis mentioned in the discussion section. The longitudinal association with SPARC is similar.

Time course of FM-UE without hand scores.

FM-UE without hand	Week 26		
	B	95%-CI	P
Intercept	47.8	[45.4 – 50.2]	<0.001
Week 1	-16.2	[-18.4 – -14.0]	<0.001
Week 2	-7.6	[-9.8 – -5.4]	<0.001
Week 3	-4.4	[-6.8 – -2.0]	<0.001
Week 4	-2.7	[-5.0 – -0.4]	0.022
Week 5	-2.4	[-4.6 – -0.2]	0.032
Week 8	-0.7	[-2.9 – 1.6]	0.553
Week 12	-0.6	[-2.8 – 1.6]	0.568
Week 26	-	-	-

Maximum scores of FM-UE without hand is 52.

Longitudinal associations between FM-UE without hand scores and SPARC.

Regular mixed model analysis	Longitudinal association with FM-UE without hand scores		
	B	95%-CI	P
SPARC	23.0	[19.2 – 26.8]	<0.001

Hybrid mixed model analysis	Longitudinal association with FM-UE without hand scores		
	B	95%-CI	P
Within subjects effect	22.4	[18.6 – 26.3]	<0.001
Between subjects effect	40.0	[19.2 – 60.9]	<0.001